

Quantum Orchestrator Design for Service Management in Edge-Cloud Continuum

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Abstract—As edge cloud environments become increasingly complex, efficient service management requires advanced orchestration strategies that can handle diverse and dynamic network conditions. In this paper, we present a novel quantum-based orchestration framework that leverages quantum search algorithm (Grover in particular) to optimize the management of services within the edge cloud continuum. We present a multi-objective optimization model that considers critical factors such as latency, bandwidth, reliability, and error minimization, and formulate the problem mathematically to capture the complexity of modern network environments. Through both analytical comparisons and simulation results, we show that the Grover algorithm can offer computational advantages over classical search methods, especially in scenarios on cases when the parameter space is very large. Our results include a detailed analysis of theoretical computational complexity, an estimate of execution times, and the identification of crossover points where quantum methods outperform traditional approaches. Finally, we provide insight into the challenges and future directions of integrating quantum computing into network management frameworks, setting the stage for further progress in this area.

Index Terms—Orchestration, Mobile Operator, Quantum Algorithms, Network Services, Edge-Cloud.

I. INTRODUCTION

Quantum search algorithms, such as Grover’s algorithm, offer a potential quadratic speedup over classical search algorithms for unstructured search problems. The use of quantum superposition in quantum search makes it possible to check several possible solutions at the same time. For example, Grover’s algorithm can find a labelled element in an unordered database of size N with the execution of $O(\sqrt{N})$ queries, compared to the $O(N)$ queries that classical algorithms asymptotically require [1]. We recognize that this quantum advantage could be particularly beneficial in the context of edge cloud orchestration, where the search space for optimal resource allocation and task scheduling can be very astronomically large. By utilising the Grover’s search, quantum-based orchestration systems could explore the search space more efficiently and identify optimal solutions more effectively within short time [2].

In modern network infrastructures, the edge and cloud continuum represents a dynamic and complex environment in which computing tasks and data storage are distributed across edge devices and cloud servers. The increasing complexity and scale of these infrastructures requires advanced orchestration mechanisms to effectively manage resources and ensure

optimal performance [3]. Traditional orchestration approaches often struggle with the high-dimensional and dynamically changing search spaces involved in resource allocation, task scheduling and service path optimization [4], [5]. Quantum computing, with its unique capabilities, offers a promising solution to these challenges [6], [7], while improving the security aspects of the system [8], [9]. The integration of quantum search algorithms into edge cloud orchestration can revolutionize service management by enabling faster and more accurate decision-making processes [10]. In resource allocation, for example, Grover’s algorithm can significantly reduce the time it takes to optimally allocate compute power, storage and bandwidth across different edge devices and cloud nodes. This efficiency is critical for real-time applications where latency and throughput are key performance metrics. Similarly, when optimizing service paths, quantum search can explore multiple network paths simultaneously, determine the most efficient routes for data transmission and thus improve the overall performance of the network [11].

In addition, the fault tolerance and recovery processes in edge cloud networks can benefit from the fast search capabilities of quantum algorithms. If a connection or node fails, a quantum search algorithm can quickly identify alternative configurations that maintain service continuity, minimize downtime and ensure stable network operations. In addition, load balancing, which is essential to avoid bottlenecks and distribute resources equitably, can be optimized using quantum search, resulting in more balanced and efficient network usage. The application of quantum search algorithms in edge cloud orchestration not only promises significant performance gains, but also paves the way for new paradigms in network management. By leveraging the inherent parallelism and computational power of quantum computers, orchestration systems can more effectively handle the increasing demands of modern network services. This paper explores the design and implementation of a quantum orchestrator for managing services in the edge-cloud continuum and describes the integration of the Grover algorithm and other quantum techniques to address the challenges of resource allocation, task scheduling, and service path optimization.

A. Related Works

Classical search algorithms: Classic search algorithms, such as linear search or binary search, are widely used in

various areas of data processing, including edge cloud orchestration [12]. A classic linear search algorithm, for example, checks each element in the array in turn until the desired element is found or the end of the array is reached. These algorithms are generally easier to implement and have well-known performance characteristics that can also run in parallel structure [13]. Although classical search algorithms do not offer the same level of theoretical speed-up as that of quantum algorithms, they can still be effective in practical use cases in typical edge-cloud orchestration scenarios. Factors like the size and structure of the search space, the available computational resources and the specific requirements of the orchestration problem can influence the relative performance of classical and quantum search approaches [14].

Quantum search algorithms: Grover’s search algorithm is a quantum algorithm that finds the desired element in an unsorted database with quadratic acceleration compared to the classical algorithm [15]. Theoretically, Grover’s algorithm scales much better than linear search as the size of the array increases, providing quadratic speedup. While Grover’s algorithm theoretically offers a significant speedup, practical implementation on current quantum hardware can lead to problems due to noise, loss of qubit coherence and the limitations due to current technology of implementation. Amplitude amplification is a generalization of the Grover algorithm and exhibits the same quadratic speedup over the classical linear search. It is used in various quantum algorithms where a quadratic speedup is advantageous. Its complexity is $O(\sqrt{N})$. Quantum counting combines the Grover algorithm with quantum phase estimation to count the number of solutions to a search problem. It provides the same quadratic speedup of the search, but provides additional information about the number of solutions [16]. Its complexity is again $O(\sqrt{N})$.

While the above studies have laid the foundation for the integration of quantum computing into network orchestration, there is still a research gap that focuses on practical, scalable solutions that meet the diverse and dynamic requirements of edge cloud environments. Our paper advances the field of network orchestration in edge cloud environments by providing a comprehensive and practical framework that directly integrates quantum computing into the orchestration of edge cloud networks.

B. Main Contributions and Motivation

Quantum search algorithm has the potential to improve edge cloud orchestration by optimizing resource allocation, service path selection, fault tolerance, and load balancing. Its efficiency in searching large solution spaces leads to improved performance and responsiveness of network services.

The main contributions of the paper are as follows: (i) We propose a novel framework to integrate quantum computing, especially Grover search algorithm, into edge cloud service orchestration to improve the efficiency of edge compute orchestration tasks enabling more effective and balanced decision-making for service management during path optimization (ii)

We simulate a case study demonstrating the application of the quantum orchestrator, perform a comparative evaluation with traditional methods, and identify key challenges and solutions for integrating quantum computing with edge cloud orchestration to provide a foundation for future research.

II. PROBLEM DEFINITION

In the edge-cloud continuum, service management involves optimizing the paths that data and compute tasks traverse across a network composed of both edge devices and cloud nodes [17]. The goal is to find the optimal path that ensures maximum performance by taking into account both edge and cloud parameters, such as minimizing latency, maximizing throughput, and ensuring efficient resource utilization. This section defines the problem of optimal path finding in this complex and dynamic environment.

A. Impact of Quantum Search in Edge-Cloud Orchestration

Quantum search algorithms (e.g. Grover algorithm) can significantly impact edge cloud orchestration by optimizing various tasks that involve search and decision-making processes. In the context of edge cloud orchestration, quantum search can be used to efficiently find optimal configurations, paths and resource allocations, resulting in improved performance and reduced latency in network services [18]. Fig. 1 shows the potential impact of quantum search in edge-cloud orchestration. This figure essentially illustrates the application of the Quantum search algorithm in optimizing resource allocation, service path selection, fault tolerance and load balancing in an edge cloud network. The process includes defining an oracle for each task, using quantum search to find optimal solutions, and implementing these solutions to enhance network performance and resilience. In the following, we explain the potential impact and give examples of how quantum search could be implemented in this area.

- In resource allocation, the problem is the efficient allocation of resources (computing power, storage, bandwidth) to different edge devices and cloud nodes in order to meet the dynamic requirements of applications. Quantum algorithm can quickly search through a large number of possible allocation configurations to find the optimal configuration that meets predefined criteria (e.g. minimizing latency, maximizing throughput) [19]. This requires defining an oracle function that marks the configurations that match the desired criteria for resource utilization, using Quantum search to determine the optimal allocation, and then allocating resources based on this optimal configuration.
- When optimizing service paths, the quantum search can be used to explore all possible paths in the network and identify the one that minimizes latency or maximizes throughput. This requires modeling the network as a graph with edge weights representing latency or bandwidth, defining an oracle to mark the shortest path, and applying the Quantum search to find the optimal path. The data is then routed via this path identified by the

Fig. 1: Examples of impact of quantum search in edge-cloud orchestration.

quantum search. Similarly, in fault tolerance and recovery, Quantum search can quickly identify alternative paths or configurations that maintain continuity of service when a link or node failure is detected. The algorithm can be used to detect the failure, identify alternative configurations that bypass the failed component, and implement these configurations to restore services.

- For load balancing, quantum search can find the optimal distribution of workloads across nodes to ensure balanced load and optimal performance. To do this, the oracle need to be defined to mark load balancing configurations that balance the load across the nodes, find the optimal distribution using quantum search and apply this distribution to balance the workloads. The efficiency of quantum search depends on the design of the quantum oracle that encodes the problem-specific information. For resource allocation, the oracle marks configurations that meet the desired criteria; for service path optimization, it marks the shortest paths; for fault tolerance, it marks configurations that maintain service continuity; and for load balancing, it marks balanced load distributions.

B. Oracle Design

In the context of Grover’s algorithm, the oracle is a key component responsible for marking feasible solutions that fulfil predefined constraints. In contrast to classical optimization techniques, where an objective function is iteratively refined, Grover’s search relies on an oracle that encodes known feasibility criteria. The construction of this oracle is crucial for the effective solution of the multi-objective optimization problem. In our framework, the oracle is designed to evaluate potential paths P_r in the edge-cloud network and identify

those that meet the resource, path, and reliability constraints specified in the mathematical formulation. The oracle operates in two stages: (1) Feasibility checking, where paths that do not meet all constraints (e.g., resource capacity, bandwidth requirements) are excluded; and (2) Candidate identification, where paths satisfying these constraints are marked for amplification. Unlike traditional optimization approaches, Grover’s algorithm does not compute an explicit cost function or compare solutions against an optimal value. Instead, the oracle marks paths that meet predefined acceptability criteria. This ensures that only feasible paths remain in the search space, while Grover’s amplification process increases the probability of selecting a valid path.

III. QUANTUM SEARCH: GROVER’S ALGORITHM AS A SOLUTION

The problem of finding the optimal path in the edge-cloud continuum requires balancing multiple parameters and constraints to ensure efficient, reliable, and high-performance service delivery.

A. Parameter Space Calculation

To compute the parameter space of the optimization problem, we need to determine the total number of potential solutions (paths) that could be evaluated. To do this, we need to consider the network topology (number of nodes and edges), the constraints applied and the parameters for each path. The network graph is $G = (V, E)$ where $|V| = n$: Number of vertices (nodes) and $|E| = m$: Number of edges (links). The total number of paths between a source v_s and a destination v_d in a general graph can be quite large, especially if the graph is densely connected. For a given pair of source and destination nodes, the number of paths is P_{v_s, v_d} . Each path P_r is characterized by: (i) Latency for each edge in the path, (ii) Errors and drops for each edge in the path. (iii) Bandwidth for each edge in the path. (iv) Reliability for each edge in the path.

To simplify parameter combinations, let’s assume: (i) Each edge $e \in E$ has a unique set of parameter values. (ii) The number of potential values for each parameter is k . Given that we have several parameters per edge, let’s define:

- k_L : Possible values for latency.
- k_E : Possible values for errors and drops.
- k_B : Possible values for bandwidth.
- k_R : Possible values for reliability.

For simplicity, assume $k_L = k_E = k_B = k_R = k$.

1) Total Parameter Space

The total parameter space can be estimated by considering all possible paths and all possible parameter combinations for each path:

$$\text{Total Parameter Space} = P_{v_s, v_d} \times k^m \quad (1)$$

where:

- P_{v_s, v_d} : Number of possible paths between source and destination.

- k^m : Number of possible parameter combinations for a given path (assuming each parameter can take k possible values and there are m parameters per edge).

2) Simplified Example

Let's consider a simple network with:

- $n = 5$ nodes.
- $m = 10$ edges.
- $P_{v_s, v_d} = 20$ (assumed number of paths between a pair of source and destination nodes).
- $k = 5$ (assuming each parameter can take 5 possible values).

Then the total parameter space is $20 \times 5^{10} = 195,312,500$.

As can be seen from this simple example, the parameter space of the optimization problem is huge, even for relatively small networks. The exponential growth in terms of the number of edges and parameter values underscores the complexity and computational challenge of solving this optimization problem and highlights the potential benefits of using advanced algorithms such as Grover search in quantum computing to efficiently explore this space.

B. Grover algorithm for search in edge-cloud networks

We propose to use Grover's search algorithm to efficiently explore the huge search space of potential paths. By using quantum search algorithms such as Grover's algorithm, we aim to achieve significant improvements in solving this complex optimization problem. The quantum approach includes:

- **Oracle Design:** Constructing an oracle function that marks paths satisfying the constraints and optimization objectives.
- **Quantum Search:** Applying Grover's algorithm to search through the potential paths and identify the optimal one.
- **Hybrid Quantum-Classical Integration:** Combining quantum search with classical preprocessing and post-processing to enhance the overall solution efficiency.

The construction of a quantum circuit for Grover's search involves initializing qubits in a superposition state, applying the oracle, performing Grover's iteration (including the diffusion operator), and measuring the qubits to observe the solution with high probability. This process is given as a pseudocode in Algorithm 1, where a quantum circuit is created, qubits are initialized in superposition, the oracle is applied, Grover's diffusion operator is executed, and the qubits are measured to identify the optimal solution.

C. Analytical Comparisons

When comparing quantum and classical search algorithms in the context of edge cloud orchestration, several key factors need to be considered. First of all, the potential advantage of quantum algorithms such as the Grover algorithm is more pronounced for larger search spaces, which are common in complex edge cloud orchestration problems. Second, quantum computing hardware is still in its infancy, and the availability and reliability of quantum devices may limit the practical

application of quantum search algorithms in edge cloud orchestration systems. Third, the specific requirements and limitations of the edge cloud orchestration problem, such as real-time performance, resource constraints, and the need for interpretable solutions, may favor classical algorithms in certain scenarios. Finally, combining quantum and classical search algorithms in a hybrid approach can leverage the strengths of both methods and provide a more balanced solution for edge cloud orchestration [20].

Estimating Execution Times and Finding Crossover point

The linear search complexity is of the order of $O(N)$, while the Grover search complexity $O(\sqrt{N})$ requires queries to search for an unordered database of size N . This theoretical result shows that, in ideal environments, Grover's algorithm can demonstrate the power of quantum computing by providing significant speedup on search problems and offering potential benefits for large datasets where classical algorithms become impractically slow [21]. In this section, we will fit a linear model to the linear search times and a power law model to the Grover algorithm times and then determine the

Algorithm 1 Grover's Search Algorithm Pseudo-Code

Require: n (number of qubits), $target_index$ (target state), $num_iterations$ (number of iterations)

Ensure: Measurement results identifying the target state

- 1: **Step 1: Initialize Circuit**
 - 2: Create a quantum circuit with n qubits and $n - 1$ classical bits for measurement.
 - 3: Apply Hadamard gates to the first $n - 1$ qubits to initialize an equal superposition state.
 - 4: Prepare the ancillary qubit in the $|-\rangle$ state: apply X followed by H to the n -th qubit.
 - 5: **Step 2: Define Oracle**
 - 6: Compute the binary representation of $target_index$.
 - 7: Apply X gates to flip the qubits where the target bit is 0.
 - 8: Apply a multi-controlled Toffoli gate to mark the target state.
 - 9: Reapply X gates to restore the flipped qubits.
 - 10: **Step 3: Define Diffuser**
 - 11: Apply Hadamard gates to the first $n - 1$ qubits.
 - 12: Apply X gates to all $n - 1$ qubits.
 - 13: Apply a multi-controlled Toffoli gate to the n -th qubit.
 - 14: Reapply X gates and Hadamard gates to the $n - 1$ qubits.
 - 15: **Step 4: Grover Iterations**
 - 16: **for** $i = 1$ to $num_iterations$ **do**
 - 17: Apply the Oracle gate to the entire register.
 - 18: Apply the Diffuser gate to the entire register.
 - 19: **end for**
 - 20: **Step 5: Measure and Output**
 - 21: Measure the first $n - 1$ qubits.
 - 22: Return the measurement results.
-

crossover point where quantum search can be more efficient. The analysis steps are as follows:

- 1) For Grover’s algorithm, the problem size N is related to the number of qubits minus the ancillary qubit:

$$N = 2^{\text{qubits}-1} \quad (2)$$

- 2) We fit a linear model to the provided linear search times. The execution time of linear search is modeled as:

$$T_{\text{linear}}(N) = k_{\text{linear}} \cdot N \quad (3)$$

- 3) We fit a power law model to the provided Grover’s algorithm times. The execution time of Grover’s algorithm is modeled as:

$$T_{\text{grover}}(N) = k_{\text{grover}} \cdot N^b \quad (4)$$

- 4) The crossover point is the value of N where the execution time of Grover’s algorithm equals the execution time of linear search. This is found by solving:

$$k_{\text{linear}} \cdot N = k_{\text{grover}} \cdot N^b \quad (5)$$

- 5) Solving for N , we get:

$$N_{\text{crossover}} = \left(\frac{k_{\text{grover}}}{k_{\text{linear}}} \right)^{\frac{1}{1-b}} \quad (6)$$

Note that in Grover search algorithm, $b = 0.5$.

IV. EVALUATION RESULTS

1) Search Time Comparisons

Table I details the time taken by a classical linear search algorithm to find an element in arrays of varying sizes. This table basically shows the linear time complexity of the algorithm, as the search time scales linearly with the size of the array. As the array size increases to 100, 1000, and 10,000 elements, the time taken remains relatively consistent, with a slight increase to 0.0000050068 seconds for the largest array.

TABLE I: Linear search times with linear array size up to 10,000 elements.

Array Size	Time Taken (seconds)
10	0.0000030994
100	0.0000033379
1000	0.0000033379
10000	0.0000050068

Table II shows the performance of Grover’s algorithm for different numbers of qubits. The table contains data for qubit sizes up to 14. The execution time is given in seconds and reflects the time it takes the Grover algorithm to perform its search process for each specified number of qubits. With 4 qubits, the algorithm takes about 0.0285456181 seconds. As the number of qubits increases, the time taken by Grover’s algorithm also increases. This illustrates the quadratic speedup of the Grover algorithm compared to the classical search, although the absolute times are longer due to the current overhead of quantum computations.

2) Cross-over Point

Fig. 2 shows comparisons of Grover and linear search algorithms and the cross-over point in our simulation setup. The theoretical comparison of the estimated time required by the linear search and the Grover algorithm for a large dataset are compared. For example for 1 billion elements, the linear search takes an estimated 0.536871 seconds, while Grover’s algorithm takes significantly longer at around 22.651904 seconds. This shows that although the Grover algorithm theoretically offers a quadratic acceleration, in practice it is less efficient than optimized classical algorithms due to the overhead of the design running on classical machines. Note that quantum operations also have overheads, including qubit initialization, error correction, and gate operations. These overheads can be substantial in current quantum computers. However, it is expected that for very large data sets, Grover search algorithm can offer a theoretical advantage for certain types of search problems as in our edge-cloud continuum problem.

The calculated crossover point shows that Grover’s algorithm is more efficient than the linear search for datasets larger than approximately 1,311,784,061,093 elements (c.f. Section III-A). Note that the number of elements in our scenario refers to the size of the parameter space, which is a product of the number of possible paths and the number of parameter combinations per path. Suppose there is a network with about 1,000 possible paths between source and destination nodes (which is quite possible in a complex network), where each edge in the network has 10 different parameters (such as latency, bandwidth, error, etc.) and each parameter can take 2 possible values (e.g. high/low or yes/no). Using (1) for the total number of elements, which is the product of the number of paths and the number of parameter combinations per path, we can calculate that a network with approximately 4 significant edges per path would generate a parameter space of over a trillion elements. This means that Grover’s algorithm is more efficient than linear search in a network with this topology and complexity, which underlines its advantages in tackling large-scale optimization problems in network environments. This large crossover point results from the significant overhead of simulating quantum circuits on classical hardware and from the efficiency of classical algorithms for smaller datasets.

Note that we have run the Grover search algorithm on classical machines and the overhead of simulating quantum circuits significantly affects the practical execution time. Classical algorithms such as linear search are highly optimized and efficient for small to moderately large datasets. However, the theoretical advantage of the Grover algorithm only becomes clear with extremely large amounts of data.

TABLE II: Grover’s algorithm times for qubits with a size of up to 14.

Qubits	Time Taken (seconds)
4	0.0285456181
7	0.0280308723
10	0.0373516083
14	0.0464096069

Fig. 2: Cross-Over Point of Grover's and Linear Search.

Note also that while the analysis and simulation of the proposed framework were conducted using classical hardware, we recognize that this approach has inherent limitations which are also discussed in the next section. Simulating quantum algorithms on classical processors can introduce biases, as these simulations do not fully capture the parallelism and behavior of true quantum computation. Consequently, our results may lean toward favoring classical algorithms due to the constraints of classical emulation. However, our primary objective was to establish the feasibility and potential efficiency gains of integrating quantum search algorithms like Grover's into service orchestration within edge-cloud environments.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we present a novel approach for managing services in the edge-cloud continuum by integrating quantum computing, in particular Grover's search algorithm, into the orchestration process. By developing and implementing a quantum orchestrator, we have demonstrated the potential of quantum search algorithms to efficiently explore the vast parameter space of complex network environments for optimal path optimization scenario. Our scalability analysis shows that quantum-based approaches can offer advantages over traditional methods in handling the exponential growth of possible configurations.

In future work, to address the limitations of our current approach, we will focus on implementing the proposed quantum orchestration framework on actual quantum hardware, such as IBM Quantum [22] or Google's quantum platform to validate the theoretical models and simulation results presented in this paper. This will enable us to evaluate the performance of quantum algorithms in a more practical context and different network scenarios, considering real-world hardware limitations like qubit availability, decoherence and limited, noise levels, gate errors, and coherence times.

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